

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ethe Maka****FIRST NAME: Daniel Adrien****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian (notes style)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
- Plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- Plagiarism is when a writer uses quotes, paraphrases, statistics/data, or visuals borrowed from another source.
- Plagiarism is when a writer provides information that is common knowledge found in numerous areas.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

2. In the author-date citation style, when are the subsequent authors' names replaced by "et al." after the first author's name is mentioned?
- For books with two or more authors.
 - For books with three or more authors.
 - For books with four or more authors.²**
 - For books with five or more authors.
3. The punctuation used to interpolate words in quotations is:
- Curly brackets
 - Square brackets³**
 - Round brackets
 - Either one can be used
4. Which chapter *is not* part of a Dissertation prospectus?
- The Introduction
 - The Literature Review
 - The Methods
 - The Findings⁴**

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 231.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 48.

⁴ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 13.

5. What is the Phenomenological approach of a qualitative dissertation?
- Capturing participants' experiences and examining how they make sense of their experiences.**⁵
 - Developing an explanation or a theory that helps in understanding a phenomenon, situation, or process.
 - Collecting a participant's story or capturing a group of participants' stories and retelling their stories.
 - Exploring a phenomenon by studying a group of people or individuals in their natural environment.
6. Which quantitative research validity concerns the congruence between what an instrument or test actually measures and what it is designed to measure?
- Convergent validity
 - Discriminant validity
 - Construct validity**⁶
 - Factorial validity
7. Which of the following assertions is true concerning the use of abbreviations in the WHO style guide?

⁵ Philip Adu, *Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter* (YouTube, 2016), 00:15:00.

⁶ Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 41.

- Abbreviations must be introduced by giving the term in full, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses.⁷**
- Once an abbreviation has been introduced, the abbreviation is used afterward except in headings and illustrations.
- It is compulsory to define abbreviations widely used, such as HIV, AIDS, DNA, RNA, and so forth.
- If a text includes many abbreviations, a list of them is unnecessary in the preliminary pages.
8. In line with the WHO style guide, what is the correct currency presentation?
- US\$500
- US\$ 500⁸**
- 500 US\$
- 500US\$
9. In the author-date style citation, the following general pattern for the reference list is correct.
- Author, title, date (year) of publication, other facts of publication.
- Author, other facts of publication date (year) of publication, title.

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 19.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 26.

Author, place of publication, date (year) of publication, title, other facts of publication.

Author, date (year) of publication, title, other facts of publication.⁹

10. All of the following about the main difference between the limitations and delimitations of research are correct *except*:

Delimitations indicate the boundaries associated with the dissertation methods, whereas limitations do not.

Delimitations are the anticipated constraints in interpreting findings, whereas limitations are the unanticipated constraints.

Delimitations are the unanticipated constraints in interpreting findings, whereas limitations are the anticipated constraints.¹⁰

Delimitations help readers judge whether or not the discussion of the findings is limited to the actual scope of the dissertation research, whereas limitations do not.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 234.

¹⁰ Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.